

WHO
Strategic Advisory Group
on Malaria Eradication

Working papers

Group 2: Lessons learned from previous eradication efforts

Title

Some lessons for malaria eradication from the Global Polio Eradication Initiative

Authors

Regina N. Rabinovich (Barcelona Institute for Global Health, Spain; Harvard TH Chan School of Public Health, USA)

Matiana González-Silva (Barcelona Institute for Global Health, Spain)

Contact

regina.rabinovich@isglobal.org

This working paper was commissioned by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication between 2016 and 2019.

The designations employed and the presentation of the material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the Secretariat of the World Health Organization concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries.

The mention of specific companies or of certain manufacturers' products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended by the World Health Organization in preference to others of a similar nature that are not mentioned. Errors and omissions excepted, the names of proprietary products are distinguished by initial capital letters.

This report contains the collective views of the authors and does not necessarily represent the decisions or the stated policies of the World Health Organization or the Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication.

Some Lessons for Malaria Eradication from the Global Polio Eradication Initiative

Regina Rabinovich and Matiana González-Silva

The Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI) was launched in 1988 with the aim of completely eradicating wild polioviruses by the year 2000. Thirty-one years later, that goal has not been reached, although the reported number of wild type polio cases has diminished dramatically, from 350,000 in 1988 to 33 in 2018, occurring in two countries: Afghanistan and Pakistan. The major advance took place in the first 15 years of the program, with overall 99% drop in the disease burden (1). The disease results from transmission of three different viruses, each with unique characteristics. One serotype was declared eradicated in 1999 and the second in 2019, 20 years later. However, achieving eradication of all three poliovirus types has proven to be much more difficult than expected.

By 1988, when the World Health Organization (WHO) launched the GPEI, WHO had already engaged in two eradication campaigns: malaria, which was launched in 1955 but formally put on hold in 1969 following realization that the goal was unattainable in sub-Saharan Africa with the available tools; and smallpox, which used vaccination campaigns and implemented surveillance systems that achieved certification of eradication in 1980, turning smallpox into the first infectious disease to ever be eradicated. Veterinary medicine has eradicated rinderpest after a focused, ten-year campaign with good surveillance and an effective vaccine. Eradication, however, remains an active goal for polio and for guinea worm.

Extensive technical summaries and reports of polio science – including virology, epidemiology and vaccinology, and overall history of the extended polio eradication effort have been written (for an excellent and recent report, view: (2)). This paper instead focuses on key questions whose answers may be of relevance to the concept of a renewed malaria eradication effort, namely,

- Why did the WHO, with endorsement of the World Health Assembly (WHA), decide to engage in a new eradication effort, and how was polio selected among other preventable diseases?
- How has the program governance structure evolved?
- What are the key successes and failures over more than 30 years of intense work?
- What are the key issues that may inform the malaria eradication strategy?

Key aspects covered in the literature review and selected interviews which informed the review include decision-making and priority setting, governance structures, the role and integration of research, the evolution and implementation of surveillance systems and the processes for community engagement as the program has progressed towards polio eradication.

Background

Poliomyelitis is a disease caused by 3 types of wild poliovirus that can cause paralysis in one out of 100-200 infected people. It can be effectively prevented with two different vaccines:

- Sabin Oral Vaccine (OPV) contains live-attenuated polioviruses and generates herd immunity. It is feasible to manufacture at large scale and easy to administer, but has the rare risk of reversion to neurovirulence. This has resulted in polio vaccine-derived outbreaks, which remain a critical challenge wherever live attenuated vaccine is used without concomitant IPV (see below).
- Inactivated Salk Polio Vaccine (IPV) needs to be injected, is costlier to manufacture and historically supply constrained, but does not have the risk of reversion to neurovirulence, nor does it provide herd immunity. It is also safe and effective in immunocompromised patients who may shed live-attenuated virus for prolonged periods.

The core global vaccine strategy for GPEI had been OPV. The shift to IPV was led by rich countries which had already eliminated polio, under the ethical framework that risk was so low that the risk-benefit ratio shifted to providing the safest, albeit more expensive, vaccine possible. The late change in strategy has now been accepted as part of the transition plan for the GPEI, and requires significant investments in order to ensure vaccine supply, and program shifts to implement an injectable vaccine, or even a combination strategy. This transition in prevention strategy at the end of the eradication campaign is an important consideration, as changing epidemiology alters risk-benefit considerations and may alter the selected strategies to achieve global eradication.

The GPEI strategy using OPV resulted in a greater than 99% reduction in the burden of disease. The last Wild Poliovirus type 2 (WP2) was detected in 1999, and declared as eradicated in 2015. (3) Wild Poliovirus type 3 (WP3) was declared as eradicated in 2019 (4). The Americas had its last wild type polio case in 1991, the Western Pacific WHO region in 1997, and Europe was declared polio free in 2002. (5) (6)

However, the last 1 % of polio cases has proven to be extremely hard to eliminate, given a number of reasons that have been identified throughout the elimination campaign. In contrast to smallpox, which is always symptomatic, only one in every 100 - 200 polio infected people develop Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP). In addition, smallpox vaccine leaves a recognizable mark, making it easy to recognize individuals previously vaccinated. In the later stages of the smallpox eradication campaign the strategy consisted of case identification and vaccinating contacts, but not targeting 100% of the

population. Without a marker of successful polio vaccination, it is necessary to re-vaccinate every child, in some cases with up to 10 doses. In addition, every case of AFP requires laboratory confirmation of poliovirus, because AFP can also be caused by other related viruses/conditions, leading to a long period between symptoms and confirmation of etiology. Both characteristics – asymptomatic individuals and lack of visible vaccine verification - make the identification and containment of polio cases much more difficult than smallpox. Both of these characteristics echo the challenge to be faced by malaria, since available field diagnostics are meant to evaluate whether it is likely that malaria infection is causing symptoms, but there is in addition submicroscopic infection; and there is no visible correlate of effective semi-immunity in adults, which does effectively protect them from severe disease.

The launch of the polio vaccine campaign

The GPEI was originally launched against the background of the previous successful smallpox eradication program. The polio campaign strategy was possible due to escalation of the intense vaccination program that targeted all children and which was established as the WHO Expanded Programme of Immunization (EPI) in 1974. EPI aimed to reach universal vaccination of children against 6 preventable diseases: polio, measles, whooping cough, diphtheria, tetanus and tuberculosis. It was not until the polio eradication program expanded that leadership was escalated at WHO, to report to the Director General.

The Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) launched the Americas Polio Elimination Campaign in 1985 based on National Immunization Days and surveillance of acute flaccid paralysis. In 1988, the WHO resolved to eradicate polio from the world with the target year 2000, and this was approved by the WHA on 13th May, 1988. (7) At that time, there were an estimated 350,000 children worldwide paralyzed annually by polio in 125 endemic countries, reflecting a far larger number of infections without AFP. (8) (9) (10). The plans at launch were to strengthen the routine immunization systems and eradicate polio through EPI, therefore contributing to an improved health infrastructure and primary health care. (7)

The WHA resolution was the outcome of intense negotiations by the health community and WHO to address key controversies; from the disease to be targeted for eradication, to the specific disease eradication approach itself. Some experts argued that eradicating measles was technically more feasible, and that polio had a lower mortality rate than other infectious diseases such as measles, pneumonia and diarrhea. In addition, after the successful eradication of smallpox, there was a general consensus that primary health care and routine immunization should be preferred over new vertical programs, and some made the case that therefore no other eradication campaign should be undertaken. (11) In fact, one of the earliest and most influential critics of the GPEI was Donald A. Henderson, former director of the smallpox eradication program at WHO, who then questioned the very feasibility of eradicating polioviruses. (5)

Some scholars have argued that the decision had “more to do with the ideology of a small number of powerful and well placed players in global public health who were dedicated to the concept of so called eradication as perhaps the major tool for international public health”. These so-called ‘eradicationists’ thought that polio could be easily eradicated and would therefore keep the concept of eradication alive. (11) In the end, polio was selected for eradication more from the comparison with the feasibility and priority compared to other infectious diseases, including measles and yaws, than the prioritization due to burden. The team that drafted the rationale for the WHO General Assembly resolution proposing polio eradication was further encouraged by demonstrated elimination of polio in seven countries, and epidemiological modeling concluding that polio caused more long-term morbidity than any other infectious disease. (12) (10)

Member states at the WHA launched the GPEI, but critics noted the concern that might mean de-prioritizing core health interventions such as building routine immunization systems, neonatal health, maternal mortality or the control of diarrheal diseases, and displaced other emerging agendas such as the HIV AIDS. (11) (10)

Three individuals were key in advocating for polio eradication in the late 80s. Bill Foege, former chief of smallpox eradication at US CDC; Jim Grant, head of UNICEF, and Ciro de Quadros, head of immunization at PAHO, who was leading polio eradication in the Americas and had forged links with the Rotary International (11)

The role of Rotary International was central to the launch of the GPEI. Rotary became involved in the polio eradication agenda starting in 1978, when the president of Rotary International was inspired by smallpox eradication to set eradication of polio as the goal of Rotary’s new 3-H “Health, Hunger, and Humanity” projects. In 1979 the Rotary Board of Directors adopted “the eradication of poliomyelitis and the alleviation of its consequences” as a primary 3-H goal of Rotary. From 1979 to early 1980s, the organization undertook a series of polio immunization campaigns throughout Southeast Asia and Latin America, beginning in the Philippines and followed by similar activities in Cambodia, Haiti, Morocco, Paraguay, and Sierra Leone. In 1985 the Rotary introduced PolioPlus – the first effort to immunize every child in the world with polio vaccine – and raised \$120 million USD. During its 1988 convention in Philadelphia, Rotary announced it has raised 247 million USD, more than double the target amount. In contrast, the smallpox program had taken 20 years and cost \$300 million USD. (13)

A central thesis supporting the GPEI was the economic case, although it was presented after the WHA resolution of 1988 and has served to sustain engagement in the face of the prolonged and costly program. The core key argument was that eradication expenditures were temporary while dropping prevention/control costs would accrue ad infinitum, and that every country in the world would benefit from stopping vaccinations once eradication occurred. (14) This assumption that eradication implied at some point the cessation of vaccination and targeted surveillance has been challenged more recently by the persistence of vaccine derived polio outbreaks. Estimating the

cost of the disease and the benefits from eradicating proved however to be difficult, with results indicating huge variations from country to country depending on the standard of health services and socioeconomic conditions. The fundamentals of the economic case for eradication have shifted over time, with the demonstration of reversion to neurovirulence by live attenuated vaccine virus, and the resulting ethical imperative at very low or no circulating poliovirus forced a in elimination shift ofed the selected vaccine to IPV, as well asnd the evidence that immunosuppressed individuals , can excrete vaccine virus for years. As a result, has resulted the program to continued vaccination even years after the last case has been detected. The transition to a global strategy of including IPV in the vaccine regimen has added costs as well as benefits, in terms of protecting global populations from residual wild type transmission.

In the context of a deadline pushed back on several occasions, controversies on vaccine strategy and endgame challenged the continuity of the program. In 2006, an influential series of papers in *Science* called for a stop to the program. “The question is, should WHO proceed with its current global eradication program, in view of all the difficulties and uncertainties identified in this paper? Our answer is “No.””, said a group of influential experts in a Policy debate, arguing that global eradication was unlikely to be achieved. (8) Skeptics also suggested that the money and efforts directed towards polio eradication would be better placed in strengthened immunization programs targeting all vaccine-preventable diseases, and that the polio efforts needed to re-focus on effective control. An important argument was that, despite donor support, poor countries had to make huge efforts to incorporate these resources, and this could have negative effects on other public health efforts. They also complained that the GPEI leaders were unwilling to reevaluate whether an eradication campaign still made sense. Their proposal was to integrate elements of the polio eradication program into global immunization efforts as soon as the annual number of cases reached 500 or less, and to incorporate surveillance for AFP into the surveillance systems for all vaccine-preventable diseases. They argued that this would sustain the gains and benefit other health problems beyond polio. (5) (8)

Despite controversies, the program has continued with additional WHA resolutions following the launch of GPEI, each reflecting adaptation to new scenarios and failure to achieve eradication by 2000. In May 2013, the 66th World Health Assembly reaffirmed its commitment and endorsed the *Polio Eradication and Endgame Strategic Plan 2013–2018*, while the *Polio Endgame Strategy 2019-2023* was launched in 2019.

The economic case and true expenditures

The criticisms of GPEI have been in large part economic, based on tremendous increases in financial requirements since the original estimate of 155 million USD during 1989-2000, which was already higher than the ongoing support to EPI at the time. Resources devoted to polio eradication reached up to 25% of all funds spent by WHO in some years; in the African region, around 90% of WHO–funded immunization staff and infrastructure were supported by GPEI funding. (10)

In 2002, the Technical Consultative Group (TCG) stressed that the funding gap ‘constituted the greatest threat to polio eradication and that closing the funding gap should be the highest priority of the partnership. (14).

Different agencies have increased their funding throughout the life span of GPEI. Apart from direct donations, the Rotary was instrumental in securing the involvement of private sector partners—for instance, Coca Cola support in several African countries to “Kick Polio Out of Africa”. As well, it led the strategy of advocacy to influence government leaders in donor countries and their constituencies. In 1999, the UN Foundation and the BMGF joined forces to fund GPEI, and for the first time resources were devoted to sustain high level political commitment through advocacy actions to encourage both new donors and countries to increase financial support to polio eradication. (14)

National funding has both been an important contribution and has been generally underestimated when calculating the overall investments in polio eradication. In “packaging” its funding gap messages, the GPEI highlighted commitments from international donors but rarely mentioned the contributions in money or in-kind made by countries carrying out polio eradication activities. (15)

Governance

Compared with the smallpox eradication program, coordination of polio eradication efforts has been perhaps more challenging, in the context of a post-Cold War international scenario in which countries had a greater degree of political independence. By 2019, the GPEI had a complex structure including a number of governments, agencies and funders. Important concepts that emerged from this review was that some elements of governance were unique to the context of the health politics at the time of the creation of GPEI; others emerged in response to problems to be solved, from engagement to technical; and finally, that governance of the program shifted as the program evolved.

As the primary body for decision making at the World Health Organization, the World Health Assembly is also the highest governance body of the GPEI, issuing resolutions that set the overall scope of the programme and officially engage Member States, that ultimately are the owners of the GPEI. Countries are responsible for carrying out the activities included in the strategic plans of GPEI and achieving the objectives, both where polio cases are still detected and in those that have been declared polio-free.

The WHA resolution that established the GPEI determined a WHO-led, headquarters model, with a WHO coordinator that reported directly to the WHO Director General. Key partners were originally WHO, UNICEF, the US CDC and Rotary International. The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and GAVI were added to the group later.

Heads of these six agencies form the **Polio Oversight Board (POB)**, chaired by WHO Director General, which is the group responsible for overseeing operations of the GPEI. The POB is supported by the **Strategy Committee (SC)**, the leading body from an operational point of view, overseeing execution of activities and management and leading the elaboration of multiyear plans and budgets. It has 6 different working groups on finance, immunization systems, advocacy & communication, outbreak management and containment management, and transition management.

The GPEI also counts with a **Finance and Accountability Committee (FAC)**, composed of major donors who meet quarterly to address financial needs, funding sources and provide overall financial advice. This Committee is supported by a more management oriented Finance Management Team.

The **Global Polio Partner Group (PPG)**, launched in 2012, includes the POB agencies, donors, countries and key non- governmental organizations. Its role is to serve as stakeholder voice for the GPEI in the development of strategies and foster engagement and support to polio eradication at the political and financial levels. The PPG reports to the Polio Oversight Board; it is informal in nature and its recommendations are non-binding.

Other bodies include a variety of technical advisory groups that make specific recommendations on how to achieve success, gather lessons learned from the GPEI, and plan the 'post eradication' phase, addressing key questions such as how immunization programs would need to be modified to avoid re-emergence of the disease, what to do with laboratory stocks of poliovirus, how to sustain surveillance and integrate it to immunization programs, and how polio infrastructure and lessons learnt can support achievement of elimination of measles and rubella, as recommended by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on immunization (9)(16)

There had been a number of changes and evolutions to the governance structure since inception of the GPEI, not surprising since the eradication program was originally targeted to end by 2000. Over three decades, the program evolved in complexity, with additional partners, funders and challenges, each driving adaptation in both governance and management..[For an organogram of the structures in place as per November, 2019, see: ¹]

Several other supporting or implementing bodies were put in place over the 30 years of existence of the GPEI. The Stop Transmission of Polio (STOP) program was developed and initiated by the CDC, in collaboration with the WHO, to train and mobilize additional human resources to provide technical assistance to polio-endemic countries, focusing in strengthening disease surveillance, outbreak response and EPI system, creating a network of alumni in key areas of public health. (17)

¹ The organogram valid on November 8th, 2019 can be found at: <http://polioeradication.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/GPEI-structure-org-chart-revised-20191030.pdf>

Supported by the Rotary, many countries established National Polio Plus Committees, (18) in order to contribute with health interventions concomitant to the polio vaccination campaigns. The global and regional certification commissions at the national and regional levels operate independently from the national programs and provide enhanced accountability mechanisms.

In 2013, the Independent Monitoring Board (IMB) made a strong statement related to GPEI governance: “If a billion-dollar-a-year emergency global health program were established from scratch today, its management structure would look nothing like that of the GPEI”. (19) However, substantive governance changes were not made in the belief that there was a defined timeframe to achieve eradication.

The IMB was established in 2010 a means to “break the deadlock” in which the program had entered after a decade of stagnation in progress, and the identified need for substantial programmatic changes. It replaced the original Advisory Committee on Poliomyelitis Eradication, and consists of 9 members and an entirely independent secretariat. The key asset of the IMB was its independence and freedom to provide advice both at country and program level. Based on IMB recommendations, national or subnational polio eradication task forces were established, chaired by the president or prime minister to provide oversight and ensure appropriate management and accountability. (19) (10) (20)

The IMB has pointed out challenging issues to the GPEI governance structure, including reluctance of countries to share data, power imbalance, need for greater involvement of core partners in the program’s management and the need to be more open to a wider group of stakeholders. These recommendations led to the creation of new bodies such as the interagency Polio Oversight Board and the Polio Partners group (mentioned above). (19) In 2012, the IMB also recommended that the WHO asked the WHA to declare the completion of polio eradication a programmatic emergency for global health, acknowledging that the program was at a tipping point between failure and success. (21) The IMB has however no authority to make changes, providing only recommendations.

Leaders in the GPEI have made their own analysis of lessons learned from polio to other health initiatives:

“During >25 years of operations, the Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI) has mobilized and trained millions of volunteers, social mobilizers, and health workers; accessed households untouched by other health initiatives; mapped and brought health interventions to chronically neglected and underserved communities; and established a standardized, real-time global surveillance and response capacity.We have the opportunity and obligation to build a better future by applying the lessons learned from GPEI and its infrastructure and unique functions to other global health priorities and initiatives” (22)

When extrapolating these lessons, however, it should be considered the governance complexities emerged from this well funded program , but it has been obliged to sustain the surveillance structure and the vaccination campaigns much longer than expected, due to delays in completing eradication.

Research

Research is responsible for most of the knowledge and tools that made eradication of polio conceivable. Its contributions range from the identification of the 3 different viral serotypes that cause poliomyelitis, the ability to grow and hence study the virus, the development of vaccines, which have a pivotal role as a tool for polio eradication, and creation of genetic tools for surveillance, in addition to the key strategic changes in immunization strategy. (9)

Every review on lessons learned from the history of polio eradication points toward the critical importance of building and maintaining a capacity for research, innovation and epidemiological studies in order to have solid evidence to establish –and redirect- strategies. However, some reviews also mention that truly game-changing innovations became available only very late in the program (20).

There are key nuances to the way that the polio research program has been aligned and managed in the past three decades. While the concept that research was key to the development of the first two vaccines was easily recognized, once these had been created, it became clear that there were still other problems and challenges to be solved requiring a response by the research community. As a result, there was a subsequent creation of an independent group of experts committed to reviewing proposals, prioritizing, and presenting them to the GPEI partners for funding. An essential component to its success was the independence of funding lines between the the research and program funding, so that these were not perceived in competition. However, research has not had a committed fund nor ceiling. (23) In some ways this protected the budget, since there is an endless capacity of the research community to explore interesting ideas

The pathway to an established research framework was the result of iterative sequence of decisions.

In the early days of the GPEI, applied research projects were driven by program setbacks and operational gaps, which allowed improvement in logistics and supply (including cold-chain technology such as vaccine vial monitors), diagnostics, tools for monitoring & evaluation, laboratory methodology and surveillance techniques for acute flaccid paralysis (9).

In 1996 the Global Technical Consultative Group was convened as the first body to deal with the need for innovative approaches to polio eradication. One early challenge they took on was the risk of epidemics due to vaccine-derived poliovirus.

Acknowledging contribution of research to GPEI and with the intention of providing a more robust framework for relevant polio research, the Polio Research Committee (PRC) was created in 2008, primarily supported by Rotary International and BMGF, and coordinated by WHO. The role of this body is to identify knowledge gaps and determine research priorities. It coordinates calls for research proposals supporting the strategic plan and recommends selected projects to be funded by GPEI and its partners (20). Until 2010, this role fell under the responsibility of the original Advisory Committee on Poliomyelitis Eradication (disbanded in 2010, when the IMB was formed), which provided oversight for research and its application in program implementation (9).

Over the life span of GPEI, most research has been focused on understanding failures of the Initiative, leading in turn to novel insights and to the development of better tools against polio. Research has been critical, for instance, to assess the effectiveness of vaccines in the context of persistence of wild polioviruses despite the best possible vaccination campaigns, showing the role of compromised immune responses of vaccinated children due to infection with other enterovirus or chronic diarrhea (5) (20). Outbreaks associated with vaccine derived poliovirus were also identified with the development of rapid genetic sequencing methods allowing to distinguish the origin of the infective virus. Related to this, the global network for viral characterization is also a collaborative achievement, requiring agreements for sharing samples, collaboration among researchers and strong interactions to understand program needs. (12)

Following the eradication of type 2 poliovirus, researchers developed monovalent type 1 and 2 vaccines as a “novel” tool (since the original vaccines were monovalent and then combined into the standard triple virus OPV), combined into a more immunogenic bivalent OPV vaccine in 2009. This vaccine resulted in more robust immune response, first demonstrated as key to elimination in Egypt (9). Similarly, the intradermal fractional IPV reduced the cost per dose and increased access in the context of limited supply. (20)

Research has brought clarity to challenging situations such as recombination of vaccine virus with other enteroviruses that can cause paralysis indistinguishable from polio, as well as chronic excretion of infective vaccine by immunocompromised individuals that can act as hidden reservoirs, highlighting also the need for improved diagnostic tools to identify asymptomatic infected individuals, since every infection is relevant for achieving eradication. (9) (8)

Other research outcomes useful for the program came from the fields of mathematical modeling for decision making, new vaccine delivery strategies, and refined protocols for viral culture to reduce the time for case classification and outbreak response. Molecular epidemiology using genome sequencing and common nomenclature has proven valuable for the identification of transmission pathways and key to distinguishing indigenous from imported virus, as well as pointing to the effectiveness of the surveillance system in identifying past transmission. (20)

Anthropological research has been key to understanding factors that contribute to or challenge acceptance of vaccination campaigns and to develop strategies for special population such as migrant and mobile groups, particularly if they cross porous borders, therefore involving different country vaccination programs and making necessary specific approaches in adjoining districts, engaging local leadership. This area has highlighted how important cultural and social factors are in accelerating or impeding eradication efforts and should be explored with the specific concerns of special communities confronted with program strategies, particularly any that require combined community action. The ability to communicate with target populations when the disease incidence is so low that it is no longer perceived as a true health threat, in comparison with more urgent needs as perceived by the affected communities, becomes a critical challenge for any eradication, or indeed, effective prevention program (9)

In this context, in 2011 the implications of the role of research in the polio eradication programs were reflected by a group of leaders of elimination and eradication efforts when considering these concepts to malaria: “Malaria eradication proponents should understand the importance of combining operational and research issues. Over time in successful elimination initiatives, the best researchers will see their ideas implemented and the best implementers will continue to ask what research could further improve operations.” (9).

Surveillance

One of the key lessons from the onset of GPEI is the critical role of surveillance in order to quantify the burden of disease, monitor progress, actively search for the last infected cases and reintroduction, and support documentation of interruption of transmission.

Following the 1988 WHA resolution, WHO established guidelines for the development of sensitive systems of epidemiologic and laboratory surveillance at all country levels, focusing on detection and evaluation of AFP and data management. The global polio laboratory network was funded by the GPEI, and played a critical role at a relatively low cost, and was successful even in low income countries. In 2017, AFP surveillance was conducted in 179 of 194 WHO member states, including active surveillance visits and follow up of every case by stool collection and testing in WHO accredited laboratories. Quality was monitored on a yearly basis. The GPEI directly supports a surveillance infrastructure which includes large networks of surveillance officers, systems for specimen collection and transport to participating laboratories, standardized and quality-controlled laboratory testing, and data management and analysis systems to enable rapid, data-driven outbreak response. In some countries the GPEI surveillance is so much better than the routine national surveillance systems that it has been used to detect other infectious diseases that present as epidemics: yellow fever, cholera, meningitis, ebola, dengue, zika and chikungunya. In particular, the surveillance network in the AFRO WHO Region has been mentioned as a valuable asset that can serve as a platform for an integrated disease surveillance system; it receives a substantial amount of its funding from the

polio program and the challenge is how to transition that funding to another source.

Additionally, surveillance helped to implement the effective, coordinated multi-country synchronized campaigns which target contiguous epidemiological blocks crossing national borders, defined by population dynamics, ethnography, and migration patterns rather than by national borders. This system has also required a significant share of the available GPEI funds: in 2017, it was estimated that approximately 140 million USD were provided annually by GPEI to support surveillance activities, personnel, and operational costs (22), (16) (14) (17) (20)

One of the critical innovations which has supported GPEI has been environmental surveillance (ES), recommended as a means to attain the goals of the *Strategic Plan 2013-2018* as a supplement to AFP surveillance, particularly in highest risk countries. This system detects wild poliovirus in sewage samples and presents evidence that there are virus-shedding asymptomatic individuals allowing rapid search and detection of polio cases as well as outbreak response. These data forces the surveillance program to look for imported cases and moreover identify the geographic source of the virus. (24)

ES has also provided supporting evidence on the eradication of wild poliovirus type 2. It can detect polioviruses and compare them with isolates from clinical cases to evaluate transmission patterns. It has been considered critical particularly in high-density populations with poor quality surveillance for AFP and where it is suspected that the virus may be still circulating. ES has also proven its role in detection of reimported cases in areas where poliovirus has been eliminated (as was the case of Israel which detected a poliovirus coming from Pakistan, further showing that the risk of re-emergence will not disappear until eradication is achieved). The application of genetic tools to these samples can also detect vaccine-derived polioviruses.

Overall, in combination with AFP, ES has proven useful to characterize the epidemiology of poliovirus circulation, allowing for targeted vaccination strategies in areas of increased risk or more vulnerable populations. For instance, it helped to understand transmission route in populations crossing the Pakistan-Afghanistan border, and contributed to the development of strategies for migrant and mobile populations, as in India, where vaccination teams were established in bus and train stations, road intersections, markets, migrant camps and work areas receiving migrant workers such as construction sites. (25) In other countries, it has triggered responses when virus is detected in the environment in the absence of AFP cases, preventing the potential spread of the infection with enhanced and rapid vaccination efforts in high risk areas. It has also served to identify areas where AFP surveillance needs to be improved by indicating undetected poliovirus transmission, and has helped to identify immunity gaps in specific population groups.

However, implementation of ES is challenging in low-income countries, where the sewer network is inadequate or non-existent, and sampling sites

are difficult to establish. It requires specific technical assessment to identify the best places and timings to recover samples to ensure that data are representative and that sampling collection is feasible (key factors to identify sampling sites as considered in India include risk of transmission, poor environmental sanitation, high density, and sewage recovering waste from large populations). Other challenges faced by ES are quality control, and the inability of the system to differentiate between continuous circulation of the virus in a given area from a specific presence of the virus at a single point of time. In the future, ES may play a role in the global certification of eradication, and may provide relevant information on the elimination of Sabin viruses once OPV is discontinued. (26) (24)

Community engagement and social factors for success

As noted by the Independent Monitoring Board in 2012, polio vaccinators are the very foundation of the GPEI. They go into the people's houses and inoculate children with a substance that is unknown to the parents and caregivers. Trust is therefore a critical element for the success of vaccination campaigns. And it has not been achieved everywhere. (19)

GPEI has faced two major crises in terms of trust and community engagement: when Nigeria stopped vaccination in 2003, in the middle of rumors that the vaccine was contaminated with AIDS virus and hormones to sterilize Muslim populations, and following the fake hepatitis B vaccination campaign organized by the US Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to track down Osama bin Laden, giving a basis for suspicion that vaccinators may be actually spies.

One year after the interruption of vaccination in Nigeria, the number of cases doubled from 400 to 800, re-infecting around 20 previously polio-free countries, including many affected by conflict such as Sudan and Somalia, where organization of vaccination campaigns was already challenging due to war and conflict. Although vaccination was restarted a year later, following the visit of a Nigeria team to a vaccine manufacturer in Indonesia (a Muslim country), the long term effects of these events continued to have impact years later. (5) (9)

Relevant to the understanding of underlying causes of acceptability of global health campaigns is the fact that, as different scholars have pointed out, the Nigerian setback was not only the result of propaganda by religious extremists and fake news regarding vaccine as fertility control and contaminating agent; underlying causes for mistrust were more profound, including social and economic inequality in Nigeria and in the region.

A study focusing on difficulties in eradication polio in Northern Nigeria showed that leadership questioned the intent and goal of the GPEI, not only mistrusting the vaccine but also questioning the focus on polio as a public health priority. Key opinion leaders in the North of the country saw GPEI as 'stealing' resources and undermining primary health care and routine immunization. The fact that Northern Nigeria had been the scenario some

years earlier for the cancellation of a meningitis antibiotic clinical trial following questions over documentation of the trial and proper informed consent augmented distrust of Western medicine and free products, and raised questions regarding the government's alliances and pro-polio vaccine campaigns. All this was also fueled by internal rivalries and socio-political dynamics in the Nigerian socio political landscape. (15)

Reluctance to vaccinate children in some areas of Nigeria predated the 1999 polio eradication program. While some vaccines had been welcomed in the context of risks of epidemics, routine immunization was often considered unnecessary and even dangerous, due to the risk of being contaminated with fertility control substances. (27). Once GPEI was established, religious leaders as well as experts contributed to raising fears, reinforcing the idea that there was no consensus about the safety of the polio vaccine. The community's hesitancy to accept polio was fueled by genuine fear, internal rivalries, and unattended health problems perceived by the population and leadership as more urgent than fighting against polio. According to a Nigerian professor evaluating the situation, religious bias succeeded "because we weren't doing the right thing in the first place". (15)

Rumors of polio drops causing sterility were also rampant in India, leading to 'resistant pockets' in the Muslim community. Responses included visits to identified resistant houses by medical college interns, social workers and local influential people that vaccinated their children in public. An important lesson was that properly acknowledging and addressing other health requests by the population (such as sanitation, drinking water, health services and electricity) increases acceptability of polio vaccine. (28)

In other impoverished areas, polio eradication was perceived as an imposed, foreign agenda, not responding to more urgent health challenges, such as malnutrition, poverty, malaria, and other common and deadly childhood illnesses, particularly where parents need to pay for other basic health care while polio vaccine was given for free. It raised the concern that Rotary's original support for the global polio eradication was financially advantageous to richer countries (14) while the lack of reference in GPEI publications to contributions by affected countries may have fed into perceptions that polio eradication reflected a Western-driven agenda. (15) Addressing the critical issue of acceptability, the IMB recognized that, while the GPEI focuses on polio, parents in endemic countries have other perspectives and therefore the program needed to be integrated with other health care interventions. Studies have showed that co-delivery with oral rehydration salts, sanitation services, bednets, or vitamin supplementation facilitated community acceptance. (19) (22) (24)(15)

Finally, in conflict zones, access is the key challenge to vaccination, due to security related issues, making necessary high-level political negotiations to facilitate immunization campaigns. Underserved mobile and migratory populations and communities in areas of insecurity were found to play a very important role in sustaining poliovirus transmission (20)

These examples show that sociocultural and political aspects need to be understood when designing strategies to overcome barriers to health campaigns, and provide important lessons on the importance of community engagement and other social factors in eradication efforts, as well as the need to include them in the research agenda. GPEI developed a robust capacity for identifying communities with vaccine hesitancy and those not accessing immunization services, developed context-specific communications strategies and social mobilization methods, and forged local partnerships with traditional, religious, and community leaders. Evidence-based communication insights enabled GPEI to direct communication campaigns to the most vulnerable areas and families, focusing messages to clarify doubts and understand barriers to vaccination, which can come from every front, from logistics and geography to culture, politics, ethnicity, gender, marginalization and security. (22)

Key lessons for the malaria program

The lessons derived from this review of the history of the GPEI fall into six general categories:

- (1) Starting in the hardest places
- (2) Integration
- (3) Funding
- (4) Governance Structures
- (5) Research and Development
- (6) Social support and community engagement
- (7) Surveillance
- (8) Training & Capacity building

Starting in the hardest places

Resources allocated to interrupt transmission among the very last cases may be as high as those required to achieved up to 99% of incidence reduction, and specific tools may need to be developed to achieve this goal. Clearly, the case for eradication was based on feasibility of elimination in countries and regions with conditions for success. Elimination certification in countries poised for elimination can be a leverage and acceleration force for the global effort. In polio the certification in the Americas has also been seen as proof of feasibility. On the other hand, earlier cessation of transmission in Nigeria – that has proven to be one of the hardest places- would have prevented serious setbacks in Africa, and recognition of the challenges of high burden countries or subnational regions within the global strategy may have resulted in a more balanced approach. The lesson from polio is that these have to be integrated as compatible approaches.

However, the lessons here also point to the need to identify the potential ‘last mile’ at the beginning of the program, as global programmatic risk management strategy, and put particular emphasis on the risk of re-

importation to certified countries, which is important for both polio and malaria. Experience from GPEI advises on the need to in parallel focus on completing elimination and address periodic outbreaks that follow importations from still endemic countries, suggesting that hardest places and known “persistent sanctuaries” should be addressed early, to avoid spread of the infection. (20)

The concept of validation of elimination proof of concept may also have implications for malaria, where countries have been certified and other identified as approaching elimination in the near term. However, the proof of concept in sub-Saharan Africa may be a potential validation point for the malaria program.

Finally, GPEI has shown that mobile and migrant communities are key in sustaining transmission and require specific strategies to reach high coverage of interventions, cross-border collaboration and data sharing, as well as specific surveillance systems. (26)

Integration

While the rapid advance and program effectiveness are credited to the ability to drive and directly manage the work of the GPEI staff, the unexpectedly long course of this elimination program has resulted in late stage work to re-integrate the effort into health systems, for sustainability and maximum leverage. Most recent changes in GPEI following internal revision of processes and strategies point in that direction.

Most of the best practices were signaled by a paper reviewing GPEI in eight African countries, and are related to integration of eradication efforts with the general health systems. This includes links with other child survival strategies, support to coordination and communication that benefited both polio and other disease control programmes and disease surveillance at all level, epidemic preparedness and outbreak response, strengthening and expansion of the capabilities of the public health laboratories, expanded partnerships with all sectors of the community to address both polio and other public health issues and innovative public health approaches, including data management for immunization and disease surveillance. (29)

Many actors have called for embedding polio vaccination campaigns within other childhood immunization programs . (24) According to a study on global immunization initiatives, “shifts in global immunisation goals lead to fragmentation in the implementation of vaccine programmes at the local level in developing countries. It also suggests that global actors involved in the formulation of these initiatives appear to miss opportunities to build on past experiences and fail to learn from previous mistakes. This raises questions about the initiatives’ sustainability and relevance to the overall objective of preventing vaccine-preventable deaths”. (30)

GPEI itself has established a Polio Legacy Planning Working Group at WHO to protect a polio-free world and ensure that investments made contribute to

broader health goals after the completion of polio eradication, enabling transition to country ownership of basic public health functions wherever possible. (22) And the recently launched Polio Endgame Strategy calls for “increased collaboration with other health actors to help strengthen immunization systems and address the broader needs of communities deprived of basic services in addition to the polio vaccine, as part of our collective effort to support polio-affected countries in moving towards a universal health coverage”. (1)

It is also significant that advocacy by the measles and rubella communities for transitioning GPEI assets towards elimination of these diseases points towards a ‘diagonal approach’ that uses measles transmission as sentinel of areas that need increased coverage, and as a means to strengthening overall immunization and health systems. (20)

While a number of advantages of vertical funding and programming have been highlighted, the polio initiative has been both chastised for its vertical focus and lack of integration, and praised for its establishment of infrastructure to support other global health systems. It has also created emergency outbreak response systems that can respond to other infectious diseases, and steps towards integration seem to offer advantages also in other realms, such as acceptability by communities that, in the context of very low burden of disease as in elimination contexts, may not understand why polio vaccines are freely given while other health issues perceived as more urgent and personally relevant are not properly addressed by the health authorities, fostering mistrust. The polio experience shows that local people need to have something to say in the organization of health interventions and prioritization of problems to be addressed.

Perhaps the lesson for malaria is that critical thinking and analysis regarding the potential risks and benefits of integration for sustainability and generalizability versus faster wins taken with vertical programs, and full discourse with the range of involved partners. The polio program is based on vaccination and surveillance. For malaria, the effort includes not only prevention with vector tools, and surveillance for disease and perhaps infection, but also the need for identification and treatment of malaria cases, requiring integration into other systems such as national treatment programs and systems for implementation through ICCM and health extension workers.

In this context, a key lesson from polio, of relevance to malaria, is the strategic timing for presenting and planning for a time-limited eradication effort not exceeding 10-15 years, as sustaining enthusiasm for a longer period may prove challenging. (8). Programs that are documented or perceived to be cost-effective are more likely to engender support from endemic countries and donors, while potential cost savings from a reduced level of control activities after eradication may serve as an incentive to governments to support eradication. (10) Should the program last too long, not only will funding gaps be created, but also the so called ‘recipient fatigue’, given the efforts that eradication programs require in endemic countries with weak health systems.

Given the extended length of the GPEI, controversies reemerged with calls to re-focus on effective polio control and to reallocate resources to health systems strengthening and other more urgent health needs. Limiting the eradication efforts to a relatively short period, as was done with the successful veterinary rinderpest eradication program (which took a decade, from beginning to end), should be a strategic goal for any disease eradication program. This is particularly challenging for malaria, since the eradication target has been raised in the context of significant control challenges and more than 240 million estimated cases globally. The 2030 GTS goals aims to advance control and elimination in a defined set of countries, but does not yet set an eradication goal or timeframe.

Finally, based on the polio experiences in transition, the malaria community should examine how capacities build for the eradication effort are different than that for integration, and how this can be managed. Early analysis from eliminating countries can be potentially informative to the long term effort.

Funding: estimating the costs of an eradication campaign has proven to be extremely difficult given the unexpected changing scenarios over the life span of the program, and setting targets along with necessary investments required should build in necessary surge requirements. On the other hand, costing exercises should recognize the inherent value of in-kind contributions by countries, as well as the ‘opportunity costs’ they imply for lower income settings. Funding gaps remain a major threat and challenge throughout the life span of an eradication program, but particularly at the endstage, where disease levels are low.

Malaria is already struggling with these specific financing and positioning issues. The need for increased direct country financing has been identified, and the global financing plateau recognized. The focus on immediate gaps in assuring sustained control in high burden countries brings current burden and mortality challenges to the front, but transitioning to the longer elimination “tail” will present future challenges that must be considered in the global and country strategic plans.

Governance structures: Although concerns had been raised that adapting governance took too long to be implemented, the modification of the GPEI governance structure over the program lifetime demonstrates the critical need to adapt to the changing realities, engage new relevant stakeholders, including funders, and broaden the locus of control even for a highly verticalized program. The opportunity for malaria is to consider how the governance structure can be evolved to meet future needs, rather than responding to crises.

Compared to the smallpox eradication program, the GPEI found that the headquarters control governance model may be perceived as challenging as countries gain political independence, and donors have emphasized the value of country-led governance, making coordination bodies even more relevant. Expert bodies completely independent from power balances within the

eradication efforts can have a major impact in assessing advances and suggesting reorientation of strategies, if needed. Such independent bodies with a coordination role may be useful at the regional, national and even sub-national levels (particularly to support implementation and community engagement), but may also raise their own challenges if not strongly linked to technical and management standards.

Research and Development: Building and maintaining a capacity for research and innovation, as well as impact and epidemiological studies, has been critical to establish the evidence base for changing strategies and country policies. On the surface, with a highly effective vaccine and mass campaign strategy, there appeared to be limited needs for a research effort. However, several years after the establishment of the GPEI, an independent committee was established to identify research priorities with the potential for direct impact on the program, and these were presented to the donors for funding annually. This unique visibility and coordination of a linked “research” program – which ranged from genetic epidemiology, product development, and health systems research – is identified as one successful element of the GPEI, and contrasts starkly to the varied albeit productive research enterprise around malaria, with multiple funders and independent research strategies and priorities. The question may be not that one is better than the other, but that basic research, product development and implementation science respond to different criteria and are funded from different sources, and that a way of presenting the problems to be solved across the research enterprise may be a productive approach, as well as require innovative governance structures to be created.

The implications from lessons of GPEI research are significant, particularly for a disease as complex as malaria. First, the program should plan on a process to identify and prioritize critical problems that can be solved through a research platform as an inherent component of eradication efforts. Second, appropriate governance to link but make independent recommendations should be considered. Third, commitment to problem solving and continuous improvement of program implementation over the long term are likely to be critical drivers for long-term success.

Social support and community engagement: Acceptability and local ownership of the value of public health interventions is critical for the success of any eradication effort. It deserves special research efforts to understand factors that contribute to or challenge acceptance of the relevant interventions and campaigns, and to develop strategies for special populations and hard to reach populations. In polio, the concept of herd immunity has been linked to individual protection. For malaria, the power of community interventions that can both directly and indirectly affect the individual risk of malaria need to be carefully communicated. For any disease, sustaining interventions when risks are very low, and particularly surveillance and response in the context of almost – or zero – cases, will require a robust communications and community engagement program.

Surveillance: Different types of data are needed at each stage of the eradication effort, from the quantification of the burden of disease, making

program decisions and setting policies feedback to monitor progress, stratification to optimize program interventions, identify the sources of remaining cases at low levels of disease, and finally, documenting interruption of transmission. Novel technologies were incorporated into the global polio program and these have been critical to progress. The increasing granularity of information, speed of reporting, and capacity to ensure an appropriate response to emerging data, are key lessons from the progress in polio.

Sustaining surveillance beyond certification of elimination in countries and regions requires commitment to funding and maintaining a response mechanism at a time when burden of disease is non-existent, and in polio has had to be framed as part of a global good, rather than fall hostage to competing national priorities. How to sustain the funding during this period is critical. These challenges raise specific issues for deliberation by the malaria community.

Training & Capacity building: Technical solutions are not enough. Training of both public health managers and health workers to manage key decisions for malaria control and care is likely to be crucial to success. However, there are identified gaps in training for program effectiveness, particularly in the context of highly integrated health systems for care of the sick child. Careful analysis of similarities and contrasts between what was required for polio and smallpox, and what will be required in malaria, are needed. Good management of health programs is critical for success, and a lot of efforts and resources need to be allocated to enhance capacity in this front, particularly at country level.

Final considerations

A cross-polio initiative review of lessons learned from the Global Polio Eradication Initiative over the past 30 years is best considered in the current and future context for the global malaria effort. To put it in context, it is useful to contrast where the two programs are now, and provide a perspective on what can be learned as key decisions evolve for malaria.

Indeed, polio and malaria are at very different points in their trajectory, and each faces different and significant challenges today. Polio is at its 30 year point –more than double than originally planned -, having dropped by 99,99% the number of reported cases since 1988. It is a WHO-led effort with an evolved governance structure which places countries, funders, organizations and NGOs in a complex but functioning structures which defies an organogram. While the current number of cases is extremely low - with documented eradication of two of the three viruses - polio faces unique challenges due to biology (vaccine-derived outbreaks); challenging access to the ideal vaccine/s for the late stage effort; and transition to post-eradication systems for sustainability.

Malaria at this time, after increase efforts for the past 20 years to scale-up prevention, access to treatment, and fundamental and critical health systems, faces its own stall, still with more than 200 million clinical cases worldwide,

an unmeasured reservoir in humans, and emerging resistance. Both face financial challenges and competing global priorities.

The lessons learned, at a high level, are about the need to manage change: evolution of governance structures, the need for competent scientific assessments and recommendations, a responsive research base to help solve emerging technical and systems problems, incorporation of new tools, and program integration for effectiveness and sustainability. Finally, eradication of any infectious disease is an enormous challenge and there is a need, and perhaps opportunity, to plan to phase efforts (both targeted short term plans, and re-evaluated longer term targets) in the context of resources and epidemiology.

Selected Bibliography

1. Global Polio Eradication Initiative. Polio Endgame Strategy 2019 – 2023. 2019;
2. Vidor E. Poliovirus vaccine - Inactivated. In: Plotkin's Vaccine. Elsevier; 2017. p. 841–65.
3. Global Polio Eradication Initiative. Global eradication of wild poliovirus 2 declared [Internet]. [cited 2005 Sep 20]. Available from: <http://polioeradication.org/news-post/global-eradication-of-wild-poliovirus-type-2-declared/>
4. WHO. Two out of three wild poliovirus strains eradicated [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Nov 13]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/feature-stories/detail/two-out-of-three-wild-poliovirus-strains-eradicated>
5. Roberts L. Polio eradication: is it time to give up. *Science* (80-). 2006;312(5775):832–5.
6. Control EC for DP and. Polio interactive map [Internet]. Available from: <https://ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/polio-interactive-map>
7. WHA. WHA41.28 Global eradication of poliomyelitis by the year 2000 [Internet]. 1988. Available from: <https://www.who.int/ihr/polioresolution4128en.pdf>
8. Arita, Isao; Nakane, Miyuki; Fenner F. Is Polio Eradication Realistic? *Science* (80-). 2006;312(5775):852–4.
9. Breman JG, de Quadros CA, Dowdle WR, Foege WH, Henderson DA, John TJ, et al. The Role of Research in Viral Disease Eradication and Elimination Programs: Lessons for Malaria Eradication. *PLoS Med*. 2011;8(1):e1000405.
10. Keegan R, Dabbagh A, Strebel PM, Cochi SL. Comparing measles with previous eradication programs: Enabling and constraining factors. *J Infect Dis*. 2011;204(SUPPL. 1).
11. Muraskin W. Polio eradication was an ideological project. *BMJ*. 2012;345:e8545.
12. Nathanson N, Kew OM. From emergence to eradication: The epidemiology of poliomyelitis deconstructed. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2010;172(11):1213–29.
13. Rotary. Timeline: Partners in eradicating polio [Internet]. Available

- from: timeline: Partners in eradicating polio
14. Pirio GA, Kaufmann J. Polio eradication is just over the horizon: The challenges of global resource mobilization. *J Health Commun.* 2010;15(SUPPL. 1):66–83.
 15. Renne E. Perspectives on polio and immunization in Northern Nigeria. *Soc Sci Med.* 2006;63(7):1857–69.
 16. Tangermann RH, Lamoureux C, Tallis G, Goel A. The critical role of acute flaccid paralysis surveillance in the Global Polio Eradication Initiative. *Int Health.* 2017;9(3):156–63.
 17. Kerr Y, Mailhot M, Williams AJ, Swezy V, Quick L, Tangermann RH, et al. Lessons Learned and Legacy of the Stop Transmission of Polio Program. *J Infect Dis.* 2017;216(Suppl 1):S316–23.
 18. Aylward B, Tangermann R. The global polio eradication initiative: Lessons learned and prospects for success. *Vaccine* [Internet]. 2011;29(SUPPL. 4):D80–5. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2011.10.005>
 19. Rutter PD, Donaldson LJ. Oversight role of the independent monitoring board of the global polio eradication initiative. *J Infect Dis.* 2014;210(Suppl 1):S16–22.
 20. Goodson JL, Alexander JP, Linkins RW, Orenstein WA. Measles and rubella elimination: learning from polio eradication and moving forward with a diagonal approach. *Expert Rev Vaccines* [Internet]. 2017;16(12):1203–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14760584.2017.1393337>
 21. Centre W media. 65th World Health Assembly closes with new global health measures [Internet]. Available from: https://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/releases/2012/wha65_closes_20120526/en/
 22. Cochi SL, Freeman A, Guirguis S, Jafari H, Aylward B. Global polio eradication initiative: Lessons learned and legacy. *J Infect Dis.* 2014;210(Suppl 1):S540–6.
 23. John Maudlin. Personal communication to the author.
 24. Ayukekbong JA. Current goals and prospects of the global polio eradication initiative. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2015;69(12):1133–4.
 25. Bahl S, R K, Menabde N, Thapa A, J M, Swezy V, et al. Polio-Free Certification and Lessons Learned -- South-East Asia region, March 2014. *MMWR Mor Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2014;63(42):941–6.
 26. Asghar H, Diop OM, Weldegebriel G, Malik F, Shetty S, Bassioni L El, et al. Environmental surveillance for polioviruses in the global polio eradication initiative. *J Infect Dis.* 2014;210(Suppl 1):S294–303.
 27. Ejembi CL, Renne EP, Adamu H. The Politics of the 1996 Cerebrospinal Meningitis Epidemic in Nigeria. *Africa J Int African Inst.* 1998;68(1):118–34.
 28. Ansari MA, Khan Z, Khan IM. Reducing resistance against polio drops. *J R Soc Promot Health.* 2007;127(6):276–9.
 29. Okeibunor J, Nshimirimana D, Nsubuga P, Mutabaruka E, Tapsoba L, Ghali E, et al. Documentation of polio eradication initiative best practices: Experience from WHO African Region. *Vaccine* [Internet]. 2016;34(43):5144–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2016.05.058>

30. Hardon, Anita; Blume S. Shifts in global immunisation goals (1984–2004): unfinished agendas and mixed results. *Soc Sci Med.* 2005;60(2):345–56.